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Review Article

A REVIEW ON ANTIBIOTICS¹K.Jahnavi kutty, ²D.charitha , ³Y.Udaya bhanu, ⁴Rama Rao Nadendla¹Chalapathi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh.

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Abstract:

Antibiotics also called antibacterial, are a type of antimicrobial drugs used in the treatment and prevention of bacterial infections. They may either kill or inhibit the growth of bacteria. A limited number of antibiotics also possess antiprotozoal activity. Antibiotics are not effective against viruses such as the common cold or influenza, and there in appropriate use allows the emergence of resistance organism. Antibiotics revolutionized medicine in the 20th century, and have together with vaccination led to the near eradication of diseases such as tuberculosis in the developed world. Their effectiveness and easy access led to overuse, especially in livestock raising, prompting bacteria to develop resistance. This has led to widespread problems with antimicrobial and antibiotic resistance, so much as to prompt the World Health Organization to classify antimicrobial resistance as a "serious threat that is no longer a prediction for the future, it is happening right now in every region of the world and has the potential to affect anyone, of any age, in any country". This review article mainly focused on the advances and developments in the antibiotics along with the antibiotic resistance which is a major threat in recent times. The article also depicts the importance, rational uses, classification and production of antibiotics. Along with the above information on the interactions and side effects of the antibiotics was also provided in this article.

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INTRODUCTION:

The rapid emergence of resistant bacteria is occurring worldwide, endangering the efficacy of antibiotics, which have transformed medicine and saved millions of lives [1, 2]. Many decades after the first patients were treated with antibiotics; bacterial infections have again become a threat [3]. The antibiotic resistance crisis has been attributed to the overuse and misuse of these medications, as well as a lack of new drug development by the pharmaceutical industry due to reduced economic incentives and challenging regulatory requirements [4, 5]. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) has classified a number of bacteria as presenting urgent, serious, and concerning threats, many of which are already responsible for placing a substantial clinical and financial burden on the U.S. health care system, patients, and their families [6].

THE HISTORY OF ANTIBIOTICS:

History of Antibiotics: The management of microbial infections in ancient Egypt, Greece, and China is well-documented. The modern era of antibiotics started with the discovery of penicillin by Sir Alexander Fleming in 1928. Since then, antibiotics have transformed modern medicine and saved millions of lives [7]. Antibiotics were first prescribed to treat serious infections in the 1940s [8]. Penicillin was successful in controlling bacterial infections among

World War II soldiers [9]. However, shortly thereafter, penicillin resistance became a substantial clinical problem, so that, by the 1950s, many of the advances of the prior decade were threatened [10]. In response, new beta-lactam antibiotics were discovered, developed, and deployed, restoring confidence [11]. However, the first case of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) was identified during that same decade, in the United Kingdom in 1962 and in the United States in 1968 [12]. Unfortunately, resistance has eventually been seen to nearly all antibiotics that have been developed [13]. Vancomycin was introduced into clinical practice in 1972 for the treatment of methicillin resistance in both *S. aureus* and coagulase-negative staphylococci. It had been so difficult to induce Vancomycin resistance that it was believed unlikely to occur in a clinical setting. However, cases of Vancomycin resistance were reported in coagulase-negative staphylococci in 1979 and 1983 [14]. From the late 1960s through the early 1980s, the pharmaceutical industry introduced many new antibiotics to solve the resistance problem, but after that the antibiotic pipeline began to dry up and fewer new drugs were introduced [15]. As a result, in 2015, many decades after the first patients were treated with antibiotics; bacterial infections have again become a threat [16].

CLASSIFICATION OF ANTIBIOTICS:**Table 1:** Titles of antibiotics and their examples

ANTIBIOTIC	EXAMPLES	ANTIBIOTIC	EXAMPLES
B-Lactams	Pencilins	Glycopeptides	Vancomycin
	Cephalosporins		Teicoplanin
	Monobactams	Tetracyclins	Minocycline
Aminoglycosides	Gentamicin		Tigecyclin
	Streptomycin	Macrolides	Erythromycin
Spectinomycin	Azithromycin		

ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE:**Definition:**

The WHO defines antimicrobial resistance as a microorganism's resistance to an antimicrobial drug that was once able to treat an infection by that

microorganism [17]. A person cannot become resistant to antibiotics. Resistance is a property of the microbe, not a person or other organism infected by a microbe [18].

Fig 1: Diagram showing the difference between Non-resistant bacteria and Drug resistant bacteria

Causes:

Bacteria with resistance to antibiotics predate medical use of antibiotics by humans; however, widespread antibiotic use has made more bacteria resistant through the process of evolutionary pressure [19, 20].

Reasons for the widespread use of antibiotics include:

- Increasing global availability over time since the 1950s
- Uncontrolled sale in many low or middle income countries, where they can be obtained over the counter without a prescription, potentially resulting in antibiotics being used when not indicated. This may result in emergence of resistance in any remaining bacteria.

Human medicine:

Increasing bacterial resistance is linked with the volume of antibiotic prescribed, as well as missing doses.

Environmental:

Antibiotic resistance is a growing problem among humans and wildlife in terrestrial or aquatic environments [21]. Antibiotics have been polluting the environment since their introduction through human waste (medication, farming), animals, and the pharmaceutical industry.

Prevention:

World Health Organization

In 2014, the WHO stated:

- People can help tackle resistance by:

- Using antibiotics only when prescribed by a doctor;
- Completing the full prescription, even if they feel better;
- Never sharing antibiotics with others or using leftover prescriptions.

- Health workers and pharmacists can help tackle resistance by:

- Only prescribing and dispensing antibiotics when they are truly needed;
- Prescribing and dispensing the right antibiotic(s) to treat the illness.

- Policymakers can help tackle resistance by:

- Strengthening resistance tracking and laboratory capacity;
- Regulating and promoting appropriate use of medicines.

- Policymakers and industry can help tackle resistance by:

- Fostering innovation and research and development of new tools;
- Promoting cooperation and information sharing among all stakeholders [22].

Mechanism:

The four main mechanisms by which microorganisms exhibit resistance to antimicrobials are:

1. **Drug inactivation or modification:** for example, enzymatic deactivation of penicillin G in some penicillin-resistant bacteria through the production of β -lactamases. Most commonly, the protective enzymes produced by the bacterial cell will

- add an acetyl or phosphate group to a specific site on the antibiotic, which will reduce its ability to bind to the bacterial ribosomes and disrupt protein synthesis [23].
- Alteration of target site:** for example, alteration of PBP—the binding target site of penicillins—in MRSA and other penicillin-resistant bacteria. Another protective mechanism found among bacterial species is ribosomal protection proteins. These proteins protect the bacterial cell from antibiotics that target the cell's ribosomes to inhibit protein synthesis. The mechanism involves the binding of the ribosomal protection proteins to the ribosomes of the bacterial cell, which in turn changes its conformational shape. This allows the ribosomes to continue synthesizing proteins essential to the cell while preventing antibiotics from binding to the ribosome to inhibit protein synthesis.
 - Alteration of metabolic pathway:** for example, some sulfonamide-resistant bacteria do not require para-aminobenzoic acid (PABA), an important precursor for the synthesis of folic acid and nucleic acids in bacteria inhibited by sulfonamides, instead, like mammalian cells, they turn to using preformed folic acid.
 - Reduced drug accumulation:** by decreasing drug permeability or increasing active efflux (pumping out) of the drugs across the cell surface. These specialized pumps can be found within the cellular membrane of certain bacterial species and are used to pump antibiotics out of the cell before they are able to do any damage. These efflux pumps are often activated by a specific substrate associated with an antibiotic.

Fig 2: Mechanism of action for various antibiotics

Side effects:

Antibiotics are screened for any negative effects before their approval for clinical use, and are usually considered safe and well tolerated. However, some antibiotics have been associated with a wide extent of

adverse side effects ranging from mild to very severe depending on the type of antibiotic used, the microbes targeted, and the individual patient.

Common side-effects include diarrhoea, resulting from disruption of the species composition in the

intestinal flora, resulting, for example, in overgrowth of pathogenic bacteria, such as *Clostridium difficile*[24]. Antibacterials can also affect the vaginal flora, and may lead to overgrowth of yeast species of the genus *Candida* in the vulvo-vaginal area. Additional side-effects can result from interaction with other drugs, such as the possibility of tendon damage from the administration of a quinolone antibiotic with a systemic corticosteroid [25].

INTERACTIONS:

Contraceptives:

The majority of studies indicate antibiotics do interfere with birth control pills, such as clinical studies that suggest the failure rate of contraceptive pills caused by antibiotics is very low (about 1%). In cases where antibiotics have been suggested to affect the efficiency of birth control pills, such as for the broad-spectrum antibiotic rifampicin, these cases may be due to an increase in the activities of hepatic liver enzymes' causing increased breakdown of the pill's active ingredients[26]. Effects on the intestinal flora, which might result in reduced absorption of estrogens in the colon, have also been suggested, but such suggestions have been inconclusive and controversial. Clinicians have recommended that extra contraceptive measures be applied during therapies using antibiotics that are suspected to interact with oral contraceptives [27].

Medications:

Some of the medications you may need to avoid, or seek advice on, while taking a specific class of antibiotic are outlined below [28].

Penicillin [29]:

It's usually recommended that you avoid taking penicillin at the same time as methotrexate, which is used to treat psoriasis, rheumatoid arthritis and some forms of cancer. This is because combining the two medications can cause a range of unpleasant and sometimes serious side effects. However, some forms of penicillin, such as amoxicillin, can be used in combination with methotrexate. You may experience a skin rash if you take penicillin and allopurinol, which is used to treat gout.

Cephalosporin [30]:

Cephalosporin may increase the chance of bleeding if you're taking blood-thinning medications (anticoagulants) such as heparin and warfarin.

If you need treatment with cephalosporin, you may need to have your dose of anticoagulants changed or additional blood monitoring.

Aminoglycosides [31]:

The risk of damage to your kidneys and hearing is increased if you're taking one or more of the following medications:

- antifungals – used to treat fungal infections
- cyclosporin – used to treat autoimmune conditions such as Crohn's disease and given to people who have had an organ transplant
- diuretics – used to remove water from the body
- muscle relaxants

Tetracycline [32]:

You should check with your GP or pharmacist before taking a tetracycline if you're currently taking any of the following:

- vitamin A supplements
- retinoid – such as acitretin, isotretinoin and tretinoin, which are used to treat severe acne
- blood-thinning medication
- diuretics
- kaolin-pectin and bismuth subsalicylate – used to treat diarrhoea
- medicines to treat diabetes – such as insulin
- atovaquone – used to treat pneumonia
- antacids – used to treat indigestion

Macrolides:

It's recommended that you don't combine a macrolide with any of the following medications unless directly instructed to by your GP, as the combination could cause heart problems:

terfenadine, astemizole and mizolastine – these are all antihistamines used to treat allergic conditions such as hay fever

- amisulpride – used to treat episodes of psychosis
- statins – used to treat high cholesterol

CONCLUSION:

Rapidly emerging resistant bacteria threaten the extraordinary health benefits that have been achieved with antibiotics. This crisis is global, reflecting the worldwide overuse of these drugs and the lack of development of new antibiotic agents by pharmaceutical companies to address the challenge. Antibiotic-resistant infections place a substantial health and economic burden on the U.S. health care system and population. Coordinated efforts to implement new policies, renew research efforts, and pursue steps to manage the crisis are greatly needed.

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